

School Ownership and Funding Practices as Tools for Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated school ownership and funding practices as tools for effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated. The descriptive research design of the ex-post facto type was adopted. The population comprised all the 489 principals of public secondary schools in Delta State; and a sample of 50 was drawn. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled, "School Ownership and Funding Practices for Effective Administration of Secondary Schools Questionnaire". This was validated by experts and a reliability index of 0.78 was established using test-retest method adopting the Pearson (r) statistics. To analyze the data, mean ratings and rank order were used to answer the research questions while z-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that school ownership and identified funding practices (community contributions, sundry fees/levies, supports from alumni, philanthropists, incomes from uniforms, extra lessons) all to a high extent influence effective administration of schools. It was suggested that government should provide principals with funds, human and material resources necessary for effective service delivery, and principals should be innovative in exploring further funding avenues to augment government's efforts.

Keywords: School Ownership, Funding Practices, Principals, Effective Administration, School.

Introduction

Education, especially formal education plays a very critical role in human capital development as well as the functioning of a progressive society the world over. For this reason, government at all levels (federal, state and local) make frantic efforts in order to provide and manage education for its citizenry. Almost all countries of the world including Nigeria have taken education as an instrument 'par excellence' for effecting national development (FRN, 2014; Nwonkwo, 2020). Okonta (2016) observed that many developing nations including Nigeria have come to the realization that education is the key to their social, economic and political development; and as such, their developmental level is dependent on the skills and knowledge acquired by its citizens

through education. It is in this regard that government, other institutions and all stakeholders in the educational sector have taken the issue of funding as one of the banes hindering the effective operations of the educational sector in Nigeria.

Nigerian decentralized system of education has made it possible for individuals, corporate organizations, religious organizations as well as government at various levels to claim ownership of various institutions of learning across the different levels of education (primary, secondary and tertiary). The history of education in Nigeria shows that the early schools were founded and owned by various missions – Church Missionary Society (CMS), Roman Catholic Mission, Methodist and the Baptist mission – who came to evangelize Africa in the early 19th century (Abamba, 2018). Funding of the early schools then was by the home missions and contributions from the Church members. Before 1882, government’s financial assistance to the missions was very irregular and unstable; but the 1882 Education Ordinance made provisions for colonial government’s participation in education in all the British Colonies in West Africa (Abamba, 2018). This was the genesis of government’s intervention in educational matters in Nigeria; and after several educational ordinances and codes, the federal government took over schools from their previous owners/proprietors (religious groups) in 1970 because education was thought to be a huge government venture and no longer a private enterprise (Abamba, 2018). Government takeover of all educational institutions between 1970 and 1973 made financing of education to be the responsibility of tax payers (Akpotu, 2014). It is worthy to note that when it was apparent that the government could no longer fund education, the late 1980s till quite recently have witnessed the gradual return of schools back to their original owners.

The importance of adequate funding in any organization cannot be over-emphasized and the educational sector cannot be an exception. For educational institutions to achieve their major goals and be able to contribute to the economic, social and political development of the nation, adequate funding is a desideratum as these institutions cannot function effectively without the necessary funds required for the day-to-day administration of the school system. Ebong (2006) sees money as the fuel and lubricant that would propel any organization to achieve its set goals; while Amadi (2021) believes that funding should be seen as the ‘life wire’ of all successful institutions and that the importance of money in any establishment cannot be underestimated if the establishment must actualize its set goals. Funding practices therefore are the various sources and strategies of funding education for optimal achievement of the sector’s goals. There are basically two sources from which secondary education is being funded (Elujekwute et al., 2021; Nkedishu et al., 2024). These, according to them are obligatory and alternative sources. The obligatory sources are the federal and state governments as they are constitutionally required to finance education (FRN, 2014), while the alternative sources include free grants donors, corporate organizations, Education Trust Fund (ETF), school fees and levies amongst others.

As noted in the National Policy on Education cited above, secondary education is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. It is a six-year programme, given in two stages, that is, three-year junior and three-year senior secondary school; and the broad goals as enunciated in the policy statement are that secondary education

shall be to prepare the individual for: a) useful living within the society and b) higher education. These are the broad goals amongst other specific goals.

The word, 'effective' as defined by Hornby (2010) refers to producing a result that is intended or successful. As such, effectiveness can only be attained when intended or expected results are achieved. Effective administration of secondary schools in Nigeria lies in the hands of the principals, their management teams and the teachers. Jimoh (2013) posits that the purpose of school administration entails the organization and coordination of the efforts of the members of the school system towards achievement of the predetermined goals of the system. Effective school administration may be seen as the school administrator's ability to source for and provide resources needed to promote teaching and learning in the school and utilizing these resources maximally for the attainment of the school's goals (Akeke, 2019). The resources to be managed include teaching and non-teaching staff, instructional facilities, the physical facilities (buildings, classrooms, laboratories, offices) and the school finances. Adequate management of these resources in addition to the principal's administrative prowess is what results in effective administration of the school system. Therefore, for the school administrator (principal) to succeed in the achievement of set goals, he is expected to perform certain specific functions. These are summarized by Jimoh (2013), Nakpodia (2017), Peretomode (2019) and Nkedishu (2022) to include but not limited to his duties and responsibilities to his students, staff, the school community, supervision of instruction and curriculum development, management of the school finances and businesses, management of the school plant and other general tasks bordering on the day-to-day running of the school. As noted by Akomolafe (2012), principal's administrative effectiveness has to do with those positive actions (efforts) he puts in the day-to-day running of the school geared towards the accomplishment of the school's stated goals. The principal's leadership role in the performance of his duties with respect to decision making, delegation of duties to his subordinates, motivation of staff and students, setting good examples, and so on, are all efforts geared towards providing a conducive learning environment for the achievement of the school goals.

It has been argued that the principal's gender can influence his or her administrative effectiveness in the school system. Walson and Vita-Agundu (2023) study on gender and educational qualification as correlates of principals' performance in the management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State revealed that the correlation coefficient between gender and principals' performance was substantial; and that male principals were more effective than their female counterparts in the management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Again, Umoh's (n.d.) study on gender and age as correlates of the administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals in Akwa Ibom State showed that the administrative effectiveness of male and female principals cannot be the same as male principals have the stamina and ability; and can work even under pressure and other interfering factors longer than their female counterparts. In another development, Olaleye (2001) in his study on sex difference of principals and their effectiveness in school-community relations as perceived by teachers in Osun State reported that gender has no impact on principals' ability to establish good school-community

relations; as both male and female principals performed equally well and employed similar leadership behavior in this regard.

School Ownership and Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools

School ownership entails the exclusive rights to possess a school. It confers on the owner the rights to establish, control and coordinate the overall administration of the school. Amaechina, Obioha and Obioha (2020) noted that funding of post primary education depends on who owns and manages the schools. Furthermore, they remarked that private schools are funded by their proprietor(tress) while public schools are funded by government in conjunction with private /corporate bodies and the local communities; and that the constitutional responsibility of funding public secondary schools as enshrined in the 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria rests with the state governments. In Nigeria, the educational system allows for two kinds of schools divided into public and private schools. Public schools are those institutions that are established, funded and administered by public education authorities; and so they are owned and controlled by the government. The private schools, on the other hand, are those that are established, funded, controlled and administered by private individuals, organizations such as religious groups and other institutions such as universities running staff schools, for example, Delta State University Staff School, University of Benin Staff School, to mention but a few.

The impact of school ownership influences effective administration of schools. Okosun and Isabu (2023) emphasized that students experience cognitive decline and emotional instability in environments where educational supplies are scarce; and that when a teacher connects effectively with the learners, the learning environment in the classroom is favourable and students do well in their academic work. Again, the authors believed that private involvement in the business of school management has resulted in greater efficiency and responsiveness to parents' demands; freedom to manage than the public schools in terms of hiring and compensating staff (teachers and non-teachers); introduction of incentives to motivate staff for performance; adoption and application of their personal discretion to curricula and improvement in their instructional methods. Arguments in support of public schools claimed that they promote fairness, equity and social cohesion in a society. To the proponents of these arguments, private schools erode social cohesion and that feeling of belonging among various socio-economic groups (OECD, cited by Okosun and Isabu, 2023).

Funding Practices and Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools

Funding of Nigerian public secondary schools is basically the prerogative of state governments constitutionally; through its agencies – the Ministry of Education and the School Boards. Elujekwute, et al (2021) noted that government sources of fund are mainly the allocation from federation account, the state's share of Value Added Tax (VAT) and other revenues generated within the state from local taxes. Furthermore, the authors gave a purview of other funding practices through which the school administrator can generate funds to augment government's budgetary allocations in the administration of secondary schools. They include, but not limited to aids from Non-Governmental Organizations such as UNICEF, UNESCO, Ford Foundation Canada, Alumni Associations and Parents' Teachers' Associations (PTA). Also, UNESCO

(1990) had declared, “Education for All is the Business for All”. Therefore, in view of this declaration, funding and provision of quality education is the responsibility of all – government, non-governmental agencies, philanthropists, stakeholders and so on.

In Amaechina, Obioha and Obioha (2020) study on “Alternative Sources of Funding Secondary Education in Enugu Education Zone”, findings revealed that community fund schools by erecting structures; development partners, age-grades and market women help in funding secondary schools; alumni provide funds for construction of administrative blocks, libraries and recreation parks for their alma matta; sports levies were used for procuring and distributing schools’ and sports equipment and income from agricultural produce were used for funding activities in schools. In the same vein, Akeke’s (2019) study on “Funding as a Determinant of Secondary Education Effectiveness in Cross River State, Nigeria from 2006 -2016”, indicated that PTA and community contributions have a great deal of influence on funding of secondary education in Cross River State with schools having high income support from these sources performing better than their counterparts in their external examinations; as they were able to procure instructional materials to facilitate teaching and learning. Similarly, Nwafor, Uchendu and Akani (2015) added income from school fees, contributions from private sectors, revenue from students’ handcrafts/arts and revenue from sale of school agricultural products as funding practices through which the school administrator can generate funds for effective administration of the school system.

It is worthy to note that government alone (at all levels) cannot fund education. Okonta (2020) noted that the rapid growth in the youth population (school age population) and overwhelming rate Nigerians crave for education have made it impossible for government to provide adequate education for the teeming population. Elujekwute, et al (2021) study pointed out that funding has significant influence on human resource management in schools, on provision of instructional materials and on provision of facilities in secondary schools in South-East of Nigeria. Furthermore, the authors pointed out that Nigerian government has not met the UNESCO’s recommendation that 26% of its total annual budget allocation be allotted to education. This is an indication that government has not prioritized education thus exposes its inadequacies in the funding of public schools. Under these situations, effective administration of public senior secondary schools has become a herculean task as no principal can coordinate the physical and human resources efforts towards the achievement of the school’s pre-determined goals without adequate funds. So, for the principal to succeed in the day-to-day administration of the school’s activities, he must explore other funding practices outside the government’s obligatory sources.

Statement of the Problem

Education is a social, public and an economic good. It is these attributes of education that made the government to be interested in the education of its citizenry. Since the take-over of secondary schools by the government in the 1970s; and the eventual return of such schools to their initial owners in the country, there has been a general agitation about government’s inability to effectively fund the nation’s educational system; hence the involvement of private

individuals, religious organizations and other institutions in the provision of education at all levels. This inadequate funding of the system has resulted in poor management and administration of the schools by the school managers and administrators (principals) as they cannot carry out their managerial and administrative tasks of organizing and coordinating the efforts of staff and students towards achieving the predetermined goals of the system without funds (money) for the day-to-day administration of the school system. The school administrator's job has become more and more complex than ever before as provision of human, physical and material resources for effective service delivery in the school system depends on availability of adequate funds. This state of affairs has in turn affected the achievement of the sector's goals as enunciated in the National Policy on Education. It is a known fact that several factors may account for ineffective administration of secondary schools in Delta State. It is in this regard that the major question of this study is: do school ownership and funding practices influence the effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State?

Purpose of the Study

This study was carried out to ascertain if school ownership and funding practices influence effective administration of secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study examined how government's provisions and activities have contributed to the principal's administrative effectiveness; and how funds realized from the various funding practices at the principal's disposal have impacted on the principal's administrative effectiveness.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

To what extent does school ownership influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State?

To what extent do funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

To guide the study, the following hypotheses were formulated:

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent school ownership influences effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State.

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State.

Methods

The study adopted descriptive research design using ex-post facto. The population comprised all the four hundred and eighty-nine (489) principals of all public secondary schools across the three senatorial districts of Delta State (Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Headquarters, Asaba, 2022). Multi stage method was used to select thirteen local government areas from the three senatorial districts. From these LGAs, four (4) schools each were drawn from eleven (11) LGAs while three (3) schools were drawn from two (2) of the 13 LGAs selected using simple

random sampling technique. This gave a sample of fifty (50) principals (20 male and 30 female) representing 10% of the total population of public secondary schools. The instrument for data collection was a 23-item questionnaire titled, “School Ownership and Funding Practices for Effective Administration of Secondary Schools Questionnaire (SOFPEASSQ). It was validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the Faculty of Education, Delta State University, Abraka. The test – retest method was adopted using the Pearson (r) statistics to obtain the reliability co-efficient of 0.78. This indicated that the instrument was reliable and it was used for the study. Descriptive statistics of mean statistics and rank order were used to answer the research questions with a mean cut-off mark of 2.50 while z-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does school ownership influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Principals on Influence of School Ownership on Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	Items	Male		Female		M/F	Rank	Remark
		N	X	N	X	XX		
1.	Government provides adequate subvention to schools.	20	2.60	30	2.40	2.50	8th	High Extent
2.	They provide adequate physical facilities to schools	20	2.56	30	2.44	2.50	8th	High Extent
3.	They provide adequate instructional facilities to schools	20	2.37	30	2.36	2.37	10th	Low Extent
4.	They provide adequate funds for staff development programmes	20	2.89	30	2.37	2.35.	11th	Low Extent
5.	They organize seminar for teaching and non-teaching staff	20	2.30	30	2.40	2.35	11th	Low Extent
6.	They promote staff as at when due	20	3.99	30	2.02	3.01	4th	High Extent
7.	They carry out routine supervision and inspection of schools	20	2.40	30	2.80	2.60	7th	High Extent
8.	They transfer teachers	20	3.05	30	2.50	2.78	5th	High Extent
9.	They organize recruitment and allocation of teachers	20	3.19	30	3.02	3.11	3rd	High Extent
10.	They plan the school calendar	20	3.20	30	2.99	2.78	5th	High Extent
11.	They carry out disciplinary issues	20	3.70	30	3.40	3.55	1st	High Extent
12.	They recommend the promotion of students	20	3.00	30	3.80	3.40	2nd	High Extent
Cluster Mean/Grand Mean			2.94		2.71	2.83		

The data presented in Table 1 shows that respondents agreed that 9 of the 12 items – 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 with mean ratings ranging from 2.50 – 3.55 agreed to a high extent that government provides adequate subvention and physical facilities to schools. They also promote staff as at when due, carry out routine supervision and inspection, transfer teachers, organize recruitment and allocation of teachers, plan the school calendar, carry out disciplinary issues and recommend the promotion of students. The 8th rank of 2.50 rating for government provision of subvention and physical facilities indicate that these two items are the least agreed responses to a high extent from principals. The table also shows that respondents agreed to a low extent with items 3, 4 and 5 with mean ratings of 2.37, 2.35 and 2.35 respectively. This indicates that principals disagree that government provide adequate instructional facilities, adequate funds for staff development programmes and that they organize seminar for teaching and non-teaching staff. With a cluster mean of 2.94 and 2.71 respectively for male and female respondents; and a grand mean of 2.83, it can be inferred that school ownership to a high extent influences principals’ effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Question 2: To what extent do funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Principals on Influence of Funding Practices on Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	Items	Male		Female		M/F	Rank	Remark
		N	X	N	X	XX		
13	Government subvention influences effective administration of schools	20	2.65	30	3.34	3.00	9 th	High Extent
14	PTA funds influence effective administration of schools	20	2.56	30	2.89	2.73	11 th	High Extent
15	Income from sundry fees/levies influence effective administration of schools	20	3.41	30	3.18	3.30	2 nd	High Extent
16	Contributions from private sectors as part of their corporate social responsibilities influence effective administration of schools	20	3.28	30	2.85	3.07	7 th	High Extent
17	Donations from public spirited individuals and philanthropists influence effective administration of schools	20	3.09	30	3.10	3.10	6 th	High Extent
18	Financial and material supports from alumni influence effective administration of schools	20	3.33	30	3.00	3.17	3 rd	High Extent
17	Income generated from sales of school farm agricultural products influence effective administration of schools	20	2.90	30	3.12	3.01	8 th	High Extent
20	Funds realized from school activities (Inter-house sports competition, End-of-Year/Prize Giving Day, etc) influence effective administration of schools	20	2.90	30	3.01	3.00	9 th	High Extent
21	Contributions from host community influence effective administration of schools	20	3.90	30	2.99	3.45	1 st	High Extent
22	Income generated from uniforms influence effective administration of schools	20	3.20	30	3.01	3.11	5 th	High Extent

23	Income generated from extra lessons influences effective administration of schools	20	3.19	30	3.15	3.17	3 rd	High Extent
Cluster Mean/ Grand Mean			3.13	3.06	3.10			

Table 2 presents the mean ratings of principals for items 13 – 23 ranging from 2.73 – 3.45. All the mean ratings are above the cut-off mark of 2.50. This means that respondents agreed to a high extent that government subvention, PTA funds, income from fees/levies, contributions from private sectors, donations from philanthropists and financial and material supports from alumni influence principals’ effective administration of schools. They equally agreed that income generated from sale of school farm products, funds realized from school activities, contributions from host communities, income generated from uniforms and extra lessons all influence the principals’ effective administration of schools. The 1st, 2nd and 3rd ranks with high mean ratings of 3.45, 3.30, 3.17 and 3.17 respectively indicate that contributions from host communities, income from sundry fees/levies, financial and material supports from alumni and income from extra lessons are the funding practices that are highly rated by the principals as avenues through which they secure funds for effective administration of their schools.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent school ownership influences effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 3: Z-test Statistical Analysis of the Responses of Male and Female Principals on the Extent School Ownership Influences Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	z-cal	z-tab	Remark
Male Principals	20	2.94	0.45	48	0.86	1.96	Fail to
Female Principals	30	2.71	0.34				Reject

Table 3 above presents the z-test statistical analysis of the responses of male and female principals on the extent school ownership influences effective administration of public secondary schools. It shows that z-cal 0.86 is less than the z-critical value 1.96, therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent school ownership influences effective administration of public secondary schools is upheld.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Z-test Statistical Analysis of the Responses of Male and Female Principals on the Extent Funding Practices Influence Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	z-cal	z-tab.	Remark
Male Principals	20	3.13	0.36	48	1.81	1.96	Fail to
Female Principals	30	3.06	0.25				reject

The statistical analysis in table 4 reveals that the z-cal value of 1.81 is less than the z-critical value of 1.96. This implies that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on the extent funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools is hereby upheld.

Discussion

The first research question sought to ascertain the extent to which school ownership influence effective administration of public secondary schools. Findings revealed that government, the owners/proprietors of public secondary schools in Delta State through its agency, the Ministry of Basic and Senior Secondary Education, are able to a high extent provide subventions, physical facilities, promote staff as at when due, carry out routine supervision and inspection of schools, recruit and allocate teachers to schools, transfer teachers, discipline erring students and teachers amongst other functions. When government is able to provide the human and material resources in the school system, the principal would be able to coordinate and harness all the opportunities at his disposal towards the achievement of the school’s pre-determined objectives. These findings support the views of Amaechina, et al (2020) when the authors opined that public schools are funded by the government, private and corporate individuals and that the constitutional responsibility of funding secondary education in the 1979 Constitution rests with the state governments. Findings also revealed governments’ inability to provide instructional materials, funds for staff development programmes and organize seminar for teaching and non-teaching staff to be abreast with modern trends. This supports Okonta’s (2020) assertion that government is incapable of providing adequate education to its teaming populace because of the overwhelming rate of the school age population. So, a situation where public schools are denied the basic necessities needed for the smooth running of the schools’ daily activities puts the principal’s efforts in the effective administration of the school at jeopardy. This finding also affirmed Okosun and Isabu (2023) views when the authors emphasized that students suffer cognitive decline and emotional instability in schools where the educational supplies are scarce and that when the environment in the classroom is conducive, they perform so well in their academic work. The first hypothesis tested showed that both male and female principals were unanimous in their opinion that ownership of schools’ influences effective administration of secondary schools in Delta State.

The second research question sought to examine the extent to which funding practices influence effective administration of public secondary schools. This finding showed that both male and female principals agreed to a high extent that all the enumerated funding practices are avenues

through which incomes are generated to augment governments' obligatory sources of funds that are hardly adequate for effective administration of schools. Principals agreed that governments' subvention, PTA funds, sundry fees/levies, contributions from private sectors as part of their corporate social responsibilities, donations from philanthropists, financial support from alumni, income from school farm agricultural products, funds from school activities such as inter-house sports competition, support from end-of-year/prize giving day activities, contributions from host communities, incomes generated from uniforms and extra lessons are all ways of generating funds to support the principals in their quest for effective administration of schools. These buttress the findings of Elujekwute, et al (2021) whose study pointed out that government cannot fund secondary schools alone; and that funding has significant influence on human resource management, provision of instructional materials and facilities in secondary schools in South-East of Nigeria. Findings also identified contributions of host communities, income from sundry fees/levies, financial and material supports from alumni and income generated from extra lessons as funding practices that greatly influence the principals' effective administration of schools. This corroborates the findings of Amaechina, et al (2020) whose study revealed that community fund schools by donating buildings, market women assist in funding schools, alumni contributes to schools by funding the construction of different infrastructures, sports levies collected by principals are used for securing and allocating sports equipment and other school facilities and income from sale of school agricultural produce are all funding practices adopted in Enugu Education Zone. It also confirms Akeke (2019) study that revealed that PTA and community contributions have so much influence on funding of secondary schools in Cross River State. These findings have reinforced UNESCO's (1990) assertion, 'education for all is the business of all' and as such all hands must be on deck in the provision of quality education for the teeming populace. The second hypothesis tested equally showed that there was also unanimity in the responses of male and female principals that funding practices influence secondary school administration. This finding corroborates that of Olaleye (2001) whose study showed that gender has no impact on principals' ability to establish good school-community relations in Osun State. It equally negates the findings of Walson and Vita-Agundu (2023) when the authors reported that the correlation coefficient between gender and principals performance was substantial; and that male principals were more effective than their female counterparts in the management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concludes that school ownership to a high extent influences principals' administrative effectiveness. As founders and proprietors of public schools, the government owe it as a duty to provide certain amenities and infrastructures with which the principal would be able to manage the schools effectively. Also, the funding practices identified by principals to include community contributions, sundry fees/levies, support from alumni, incomes from uniforms, extra lessons, donations from philanthropists, sales of school

agricultural products amongst others to a very large extent influence effective administration of secondary schools.

Implications for Educational Planning and Administration

The findings of the study have far-reaching implications for educational planning and administration. Educational planners at the ministry or board levels should be aware that it is not just enough to plan and site secondary schools without the necessary logistics to enable them thrive. Again, school administrators on their part, should be aware and encouraged to explore those identified funding practices that were ranked very high as means of generating sufficient funds to enable them perform optimally. Also, funds generated from the identified funding practices should be adequately accounted for and put into effective use in the day-to-day administration of the secondary schools.

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